

Providing a common base for life cycle assessments of Li-Ion batteries

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In this supplementary document, the complete LCA results are provided in tabulated form together with the embedded zip-File for direct import of the inventory data and their re-use in LCA software (ILCD format; exported from openLCA), together with a short manual about the import and use of the provided LCI datasets in openLCA. Additionally, the modified and parametrized LCI data are also provided in tabulated form.

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1. Characterization results in tabulated form

Table S1 to S4 provide the tabulated LCIA results for all impact categories (ILCD 2011).

Table S1. Characterization results per kg of battery; original LCI

Impact category	LFP-C (M-B)	LFP-C (Zack)	LFP-LTO (Bau)	LMO-C (Not)	NCA-C (Bau)	NCM-C (EII)	NCM-C (M-B)	Unit
Acidification	1.39E-01	2.87E-01	1.10E-01	1.22E-01	6.81E-01	3.24E-01	3.11E-01	Mole H+ eq.
Climate change	2.39E+01	2.12E+01	1.80E+01	8.08E+00	1.75E+01	1.74E+01	2.38E+01	kg CO ₂ eq.
Freshwater ecotoxicity	1.03E+02	1.68E+02	3.40E+01	8.61E+01	6.92E+01	7.77E+01	1.06E+02	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophicat.	3.34E-02	4.60E-02	8.83E-03	2.06E-02	1.97E-02	2.40E-02	3.24E-02	kg P eq.
Human tox. - carcinogenics	3.23E-06	6.13E-06	1.39E-06	2.05E-06	1.76E-06	2.83E-06	3.12E-06	CTUh
Human tox. - non-carcinog.	2.06E-05	3.13E-05	5.42E-06	1.68E-05	1.46E-05	1.51E-05	2.15E-05	CTUh
Ion. radiation – ecosystems	6.59E-06	8.14E-06	3.00E-06	2.30E-06	3.17E-06	1.06E-05	6.71E-06	CTUe
Ion. radiaton - human health	2.50E+00	3.29E+00	8.11E-01	7.26E-01	9.24E-01	4.41E+00	2.55E+00	kg U235 eq.
Land use	8.94E+00	8.40E+00	1.31E+01	4.17E+00	1.12E+01	6.27E+00	7.65E+00	kg SOC
Marine eutrophicat.	1.95E-02	2.21E-02	1.48E-02	1.32E-02	1.29E-01	2.22E-02	2.07E-02	kg N eq.
Ozone depletion	2.27E-04	2.07E-04	6.01E-05	6.63E-07	3.61E-05	1.48E-06	2.19E-04	kg CFC-11 eq.
Particulate matter/Respir. Inorganics	1.52E-02	1.61E-02	1.02E-02	1.23E-02	2.96E-02	2.31E-02	2.36E-02	kg PM2.5 eq.
Photochem. Ozone form.	5.08E-02	5.45E-02	4.41E-02	3.66E-02	3.58E-01	6.87E-02	6.55E-02	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq.
Depletion of abiotic res. - elements	3.85E-03	5.33E-03	3.89E-03	2.75E-03	4.45E-03	6.42E-03	4.31E-03	kg Sb eq.
Resource depl. - water	7.25E-02	8.49E-03	2.86E-02	7.57E-03	3.01E-02	4.98E-02	7.18E-02	m ³
Terrestrial eutrophic.	1.78E-01	7.30E-01	1.43E-01	1.20E-01	1.42E+00	2.07E-01	1.98E-01	Mole N eq.

Table S2. Characterization results per kWh of storage capacity; original LCI

Impact category	LFP-C (M-B)	LFP-C (Zack)	LFP-LTO (Bau)	LMO-C (Not)	NCA-C (Bau)	NCM-C (EII)	NCM-C (M-B)	Unit
Acidification	1.58E+00	3.09E+00	2.11E+00	1.07E+00	5.15E+00	2.90E+00	2.95E+00	Mole H+ eq.
Climate change	2.71E+02	2.28E+02	3.48E+02	7.09E+01	1.32E+02	1.56E+02	2.27E+02	kg CO ₂ eq.
Freshwater ecotoxicity	1.17E+03	1.81E+03	6.55E+02	7.55E+02	5.23E+02	6.94E+02	1.01E+03	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophicat.	3.80E-01	4.94E-01	1.70E-01	1.81E-01	1.49E-01	2.15E-01	3.08E-01	kg P eq.
Human tox. - carcinogenics	3.68E-05	6.59E-05	2.67E-05	1.80E-05	1.33E-05	2.52E-05	2.96E-05	CTUh
Human tox. - non-carcinog.	2.34E-04	3.36E-04	1.04E-04	1.48E-04	1.10E-04	1.35E-04	2.05E-04	CTUh
Ion. radiation – ecosystems	7.48E-05	8.75E-05	5.78E-05	2.02E-05	2.40E-05	9.46E-05	6.38E-05	CTUe
Ion. radiaton - human health	2.84E+01	3.54E+01	1.56E+01	6.37E+00	6.99E+00	3.94E+01	2.42E+01	kg U235 eq.
Land use	1.02E+02	9.03E+01	2.52E+02	3.66E+01	8.44E+01	5.59E+01	7.27E+01	kg SOC
Marine eutrophicat.	2.21E-01	2.38E-01	2.86E-01	1.16E-01	9.77E-01	1.98E-01	1.97E-01	kg N eq.
Ozone depletion	2.58E-03	2.23E-03	1.16E-03	5.82E-06	2.73E-04	1.32E-05	2.08E-03	kg CFC-11 eq.
Particulate matter/Respir. Inorganics	1.73E-01	1.73E-01	1.97E-01	1.08E-01	2.24E-01	2.06E-01	2.24E-01	kg PM2.5 eq.
Photochem. Ozone form.	5.77E-01	5.86E-01	8.50E-01	3.21E-01	2.71E+00	6.14E-01	6.23E-01	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq.
Depletion of abiotic res. - elements	4.38E-02	5.73E-02	7.50E-02	2.41E-02	3.36E-02	5.73E-02	4.10E-02	kg Sb eq.
Resource depl. - water	8.24E-01	9.12E-02	5.51E-01	6.64E-02	2.28E-01	4.45E-01	6.83E-01	m ³
Terrestrial eutrophic.	2.02E+00	7.85E+00	2.76E+00	1.05E+00	1.07E+01	1.85E+00	1.88E+00	Mole N eq.

Table S3. Characterization results per kg of battery; unified LCI

Impact category	LFP-C (M-B)	LFP-C (Zack)	LFP-LTO (Bau)	LMO-C (Not)	NCA-C (Bau)	NCM-C (EII)	NCM-C (M-B)	Unit
Acidification	1.17E-01	1.93E-01	9.38E-02	1.44E-01	6.79E-01	3.35E-01	3.33E-01	Mole H+ eq.
Climate change	1.60E+01	1.40E+01	1.39E+01	1.35E+01	1.53E+01	1.44E+01	1.61E+01	kg CO ₂ eq.
Freshwater ecotoxicity	5.70E+01	6.08E+01	3.22E+01	8.51E+01	6.86E+01	7.67E+01	6.12E+01	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophicat.	2.00E-02	1.20E-02	1.02E-02	2.21E-02	2.14E-02	2.34E-02	1.89E-02	kg P eq.
Human tox. - carcinogenics	1.89E-06	3.86E-06	1.53E-06	2.12E-06	1.94E-06	2.00E-06	1.75E-06	CTUh
Human tox. - non-carcinog.	1.16E-05	6.83E-06	4.89E-06	1.62E-05	1.42E-05	1.70E-05	1.28E-05	CTUh
Ion. radiation – ecosystems	6.44E-06	6.03E-06	6.43E-06	6.44E-06	6.87E-06	6.59E-06	6.62E-06	CTUe
Ion. radiaton - human health	2.58E+00	2.47E+00	2.60E+00	2.62E+00	2.78E+00	2.64E+00	2.65E+00	kg U235 eq.
Land use	8.28E+00	5.45E+00	7.43E+00	4.57E+00	6.69E+00	7.32E+00	6.79E+00	kg SOC
Marine eutrophicat.	1.43E-02	1.42E-02	1.32E-02	1.58E-02	1.29E-01	1.83E-02	1.59E-02	kg N eq.
Ozone depletion	1.17E-04	1.06E-04	3.67E-05	1.35E-05	2.23E-05	5.52E-05	1.10E-04	kg CFC-11 eq.
Particulate matter/Respir. Inorganics	1.04E-02	1.03E-02	9.20E-03	1.29E-02	2.94E-02	2.12E-02	2.10E-02	kg PM2.5 eq.
Photochem. Ozone form.	3.91E-02	3.16E-02	3.51E-02	4.49E-02	3.56E-01	6.21E-02	5.78E-02	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq.
Depletion of abiotic res. - elements	6.15E-03	4.91E-03	5.87E-03	5.53E-03	6.47E-03	7.79E-03	6.75E-03	kg Sb eq.
Resource depl. - water	8.72E-02	5.45E-03	2.98E-02	8.07E-03	3.16E-02	5.72E-02	8.67E-02	m ³
Terrestrial eutrophic.	1.27E-01	5.95E-01	1.15E-01	1.41E-01	1.41E+00	1.76E-01	1.53E-01	Mole N eq.

Table S4. Characterization results per kWh of storage capacity; unified LCI

Wirkungskategorie	LFP-C (M-B)	LFP-C (Zack)	LFP-LTO (Bau)	LMO-C (Not)	NCA-C (Bau)	NCM-C (EII)	NCM-C (M-B)	Unit
Acidification	1.07E+00	2.33E+00	1.79E+00	1.24E+00	5.10E+00	2.41E+00	2.55E+00	Mole H+ eq.
Climate change	1.47E+02	1.69E+02	2.66E+02	1.16E+02	1.15E+02	1.04E+02	1.24E+02	kg CO ₂ eq.
Freshwater ecotoxicity	5.21E+02	7.33E+02	6.15E+02	7.33E+02	5.16E+02	5.51E+02	4.69E+02	CTUe
Freshwater eutrophicat.	1.83E-01	1.45E-01	1.94E-01	1.90E-01	1.61E-01	1.68E-01	1.45E-01	kg P eq.
Human tox. - carcinogenics	1.73E-05	4.65E-05	2.92E-05	1.83E-05	1.46E-05	1.44E-05	1.35E-05	CTUh
Human tox. - non-carcinog.	1.06E-04	8.23E-05	9.34E-05	1.40E-04	1.07E-04	1.22E-04	9.85E-05	CTUh
Ion. radiation – ecosystems	5.90E-05	7.27E-05	1.23E-04	5.55E-05	5.16E-05	4.74E-05	5.08E-05	CTUe
Ion. radiaton - human health	2.36E+01	2.97E+01	4.97E+01	2.26E+01	2.09E+01	1.90E+01	2.03E+01	kg U235 eq.
Land use	7.58E+01	6.57E+01	1.42E+02	3.93E+01	5.03E+01	5.26E+01	5.21E+01	kg SOC
Marine eutrophicat.	1.31E-01	1.71E-01	2.51E-01	1.37E-01	9.73E-01	1.31E-01	1.22E-01	kg N eq.
Ozone depletion	1.07E-03	1.28E-03	7.02E-04	1.16E-04	1.68E-04	3.97E-04	8.43E-04	kg CFC-11 eq.
Particulate matter/Respir. Inorganics	9.55E-02	1.24E-01	1.76E-01	1.12E-01	2.21E-01	1.53E-01	1.61E-01	kg PM2.5 eq.
Photochem. Ozone form.	3.58E-01	3.81E-01	6.71E-01	3.87E-01	2.67E+00	4.46E-01	4.43E-01	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq.
Depletion of abiotic res. - elements	5.63E-02	5.93E-02	1.12E-01	4.76E-02	4.86E-02	5.60E-02	5.18E-02	kg Sb eq.
Resource depl. - water	7.98E-01	6.58E-02	5.70E-01	6.95E-02	2.37E-01	4.11E-01	6.65E-01	m ³
Terrestrial eutrophic.	1.16E+00	7.17E+00	2.20E+00	1.22E+00	1.06E+01	1.27E+00	1.18E+00	Mole N eq.

2. Detailed impacts from the electrode binder

In the main manuscript, not all types of binder that are inventoried in the background studies are compared. Table S5 shows the characterization results for the five selected impact categories for all binder types that can be found in the analyzed studies, while Figure S1 shows the relative impacts normalized to the highest scoring binder type (including solvent use).

Table S5. Characterization results per kg of electrode binder; including solvent (if considered by the study). Solv. rec. = Solvent recovery within the process (100% = solvent 100% recovered / no solvent make-up balanced, 0% = no solvent recovery, all solvent is fully evaporated to the atmosphere / flared off and has to be added continuously). Abbreviations for binder and impact categories can be found in the Abbreviations list.

Binder	TFE-PE	TFE	TFE	Latex	SBL	SAL	CMC-SBR	CMC-PAA	PVF	Unit
Solvent	NMP	org	org	Water	Water	Water	Water	org	org	
Solv. rec.	100%	n/c	0%	--	--	--	--	0%	0%	
source	Zack	Bauer	NTNU	Notter	Zack	Zack	Peters	Elling	Elling	
GWP	163.12	162.15	349.63	2.75	4.08	5.41	3.56	169.84	90.84	kgCO ₂ eq.
AP	5.73E-02	5.35E-02	2.75E-01	1.90E-02	1.55E-02	3.10E-02	2.40E-02	1.11E+00	5.88E-01	MoleH ⁺ eq.
HTP	2.71E-06	2.68E-06	1.03E-05	5.91E-07	2.30E-07	1.95E-07	8.17E-07	3.32E-05	1.79E-05	CTUh
PMF	5.87E-03	5.23E-03	3.23E-02	2.30E-03	1.83E-03	2.56E-03	3.84E-03	1.44E-01	7.62E-02	kgPM2.5eq.
POF	2.31E-02	1.96E-02	1.13E-01	1.44E-02	1.12E-02	1.99E-02	1.57E-02	4.85E-01	2.48E-01	kgC ₂ H ₄ eq.

Figure S1. Relative environmental impacts of different types of binder, including solvent. Abbreviations for binder and impact categories can be found in the Abbreviations list.

3. Inventory datasets for import in openLCA

3.1. Dataset import

The complete modularized LCI datasets (as one of the principle outcomes of this work) are exported in the ILCD format for import and immediate use in openLCA. Two import files are provided, flows and processes. Importing the flows first is recommended. The import should be done into a new database where the underlying ecoinvent datasets are already available (ecoinvent 3.2.). When importing (“Import -> File Import -> ILCD”), a folder is created named ‘Li-Ion_CommonBase’, where the LCI data can be found. The processes are structured in subfolders according the source of the original data (i.e. the corresponding publication: Bauer (Bauer, 2010), Ellingsen et al. (Ellingsen et al., 2014), Majeau-Bettez et al. (Majeau-Bettez et al., 2011), Notter et al. (Notter et al., 2010), Zackrisson et al. (Zackrisson et al., 2010) and Peters et al. (Peters et al., 2016)). The top-level processes for assessment (battery packs, but also battery cells) can be found in the sub-folder “modular” (shown graphically in Figure S2), and are listed in the following:

- Li-Ion Battery Pack production, LFP-TiO, modular (Bauer)
- Li-Ion Battery Pack production, NCA-C, modular (Bauer)
- Li-Ion battery pack production, NCM-C, modular (Ellingsen)
- Li-Ion battery pack production, LFP-C, modular, at plant (NTNU)
- Li-Ion battery pack production, NCM-C, modular, at plant (NTNU)
- Li-ion battery, LMO-C, modular | cut-off, U (Notter/ecoinvent)
- LFP-C type Li-Ion Battery, modular, at plant (Zackrisson, org.)

Figure S2. Top-level processes (battery packs) as basis for assessment imported in openLCA

3.2. Selecting default provider

Each of the battery pack production processes is modularized; the LCI source used in each dataset for the modular components is determined by setting the default provider. These are listed in Table 1, together with the dataset where the selection can be done. Since the default providers are reset during importing, they have to be checked and set again correctly before using the LCI for the first time. For reproducing the results of this work, the following default providers have to be set (see also Table S6 and Figure S3):

- BMS: Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB, (Ellingsen)
- Pack housing: Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)
- Cell package: Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)
- Electrolyte: Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF₆, at plant (Notter)
- Cathode binder: Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)
- Anode binder: Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)

Table S6. List of datasets where the default provider has to be set, together with the corresponding default provider process.

	Inventory dataset (process)	Input flow	Default provider to be selected
Bauer	Li-Ion Battery Pack production, LFP-TiO₂, modular (Bauer)	BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB, (Ellingsen)
	Li-Ion Battery Pack production, NCA-C, modular (Bauer)	Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)
	LFP-TiO₂ Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery, modular (Bauer)	Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)
	NCA-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery, modular (Bauer)	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)
		Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)
		Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)
Majeau-Bettez	Li-Ion battery pack production, LFP-C, modular, at plant (NTNU)	BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB, (Ellingsen)
	Li-Ion battery pack production, NCM-C, modular, at plant (NTNU)	Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)
		Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)
		Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)
	NCM cathode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)
	LFP cathode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)		
	Graphite anode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)
Ellingsen	Li-Ion battery pack production,	BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at	Battery management system (BMS)

	NCM-C, modular (Ellingsen)	plant Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	production, for LIB, (Ellingsen) Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	
	NCM-C Battery Cell production, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen) Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)	
	Graphite anode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	
	NCM cathode paste production; modular (Ellingsen)	Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	
Zackrisson	LFP-C type Li-Ion Battery, modular, at plant (Zackrisson, org.)	BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB, (Ellingsen) Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	
	LFP-C type Li-Ion Cell, modular, at plant (Zackrisson)	Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen) Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter) Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	
	LFP-Cathode, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Zackrisson)	Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	
	Graphite Anode, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Zackrisson)	Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	
	Notter	Li-ion battery, LMO-C, modular cut-off, U (Notter/ecoinvent)	BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB, (Ellingsen) Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)
		Battery cell, LMO-C, battery production, modular cut-off, U (Notter/ecoinvent)	Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen) Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)
Cathode production, LiMn₂O₄, for lithium-ion battery, modular cut-off, U		Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	
Graphite anode, for Li-Ion battery, modular cut-off, U (Notter)		Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	

Figure S3. Selection of the default provider in openLCA

When selecting the individual default providers of the original study in each LCI instead of common ones, the original LCI can be reproduced.

3.3. Setting global common parameters

Global parameters are defined in order to use identical common values for the manufacturing energy demand and the mass shares of battery components like housing, BMS, cell package. The global parameters are the following (see also Figure S4):

- BMS_share: The mass of the BMS as share of the total battery pack mass (default: 0.047)
- Cell_pack_share: Mass of cell package as share of total battery cell mass (default: 0.03)
- CoolSys_share: Mass of battery cooling system as share of total battery pack (default: 0.0)
- KWhelManuf: Electricity for cell manufacturing (kWh/kg) (default: 9.0)
- MJthManuf: Thermal Energy (Natural gas; MJ/kg) for cell manufacturing (default: 20.0)
- Pack_case_share: Mass of pack housing as share of total battery pack mass (default: 0.186)

Figure S4. Global parameters as defined for the unified LCI

The default values for these global parameters are corresponding to the values given as common average values within this publication; nevertheless, local parameters are defined within each dataset that use the value provided by the global parameters. In the comment field of the local parameters (individual parameters on dataset level), the original value as provided by the source publication is indicated. If the original, non-parametrized value from the original publication wants to be used, the default value from the comment field can be introduced here manually, as indicated in Figure S5. The global values then do not affect this dataset anymore.

Figure S5. Use of individual, local values within the dataset

3.4. Import files in ILCD format

The complete inventory datasets (ILCD format) for direct import into LCA software can be downloaded free of charge from:

<https://lci-database.hiu-batteries.de>

The datasets were exported and tested with openLCA 1.6 and ecoinvent 3.2. and can be imported following previous instructions.

4. LCI data in tabulated form

If direct import into LCA software is not practicable, the tabulated LCI can also be used. These are provided in Tables S6 – S30. The parameters used in the tables are the global common parameters as described in Section 3.3. Inventories for components that are not tabulated explicitly are not modified and can be taken directly from the original publication: (Bauer, 2010; Ellingsen et al., 2014; Majeau-Bettez et al., 2011; Notter et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2016; Zackrisson et al., 2010). These are indicated with the author's name in the 'Provider' column of each table.

4.1. LMO battery

The inventory data for the LMO battery is based on the work by Notter et al. (Notter et al., 2010) and provided in Tables S6-S10

Table S6. LCI of LMO-C type Li-ion battery pack (Notter)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	Pack_housing	kg
LMO-C type Li-Ion Cell	Battery cell, LMO-C, battery production, modular (Notter)	1-(BMS+ Pack_housing+CoolSyst)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Li-ion battery, LMO (Notter)	Li-ion battery, LMO (Notter)	1.00	kg

Table S7. LCI of LMO-C type Li-Ion battery cell (Notter)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Anode, graphite, for Li-Ion battery	Graphite anode, for Li-Ion battery (Notter)	0.4011/(1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
battery separator	market for battery separator	0.053655/(1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Cathode, LiMn2O4, for lithium-ion battery	Cathode production, LiMn2O4, for lithium-ion battery	0.32686/(1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Cell container, Li-Ion battery,	Cell container production, pouch	Cell_pack* 1.0525	kg

at plant	incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)		
chemical factory, organics	market for chemical factory, organics	4.0E-10/(1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	p
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF6, at plant nitrogen, liquid	Electrolyte for Li-Ion battery, 1M LiPF6, at plant (Notter) market for nitrogen, liquid	(0.15957+0.019037)/ (1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
used Li-ion battery	market for used Li-ion battery	0.01/(1-8.97750E-02)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
		-0.0525/(1-0.089775)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
LMO-C type Li-Ion Cell (Notter)	LMO-C type Li-Ion Cell (Notter)	1.00	kg

Table S8. LCI of graphite anode for LMO-C type Li-Ion battery cell (Notter)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.000	kg
binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0.019	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black carbon black	0.016	kg
chemical factory, organics	market for chemical factory, organics	4.00E-10	Item(s)
copper	market for copper	0.524	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	2.00E-03	kWh
graphite, battery grade	market for graphite, battery grade	0.494	kg
heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas	1.220	MJ
sheet rolling, copper	market for sheet rolling, copper	0.524	kg
sulfuric acid	market for sulfuric acid	0.081	kg
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	-1.10E-04	m3
water, deionised, from tap water, at user	market for water, deionised, from tap water, at user	0.424	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Anode, graphite, for Li-Ion battery	Anode, graphite, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Notter)	1.00	kg

Table S9. LCI of LiMn₂O₄ cathode for LMO-C type Li-Ion battery cell (Notter)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
aluminium, wrought alloy	market for aluminium, wrought alloy	0.393	kg
binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.010	kg
binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR (Peters)	0.000	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black	0.026	kg
chemical factory, organics	market for chemical factory, organics	4.00E-10	Item(s)
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	2.00E-03	kWh
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	market group for heat, district or industrial, natural gas	0.646	MJ
lithium manganese oxide	market for lithium manganese oxide	0.623	kg
residue from shredder fraction from manual dismantling	market for residue from shredder fraction from manual dismantling	-0.053	kg
sheet rolling, aluminium	market for sheet rolling, aluminium	0.393	kg
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.130	kg
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	-1.10E-04	m3
water, deionised, from tap water, at user	market for water, deionised, from tap water, at user	0.200	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			

Cathode, LiMn ₂ O ₄ , for lithium-ion battery	Cathode, LiMn ₂ O ₄ , for lithium-ion battery, modular (Notter)	1.00	kg
Water		0.012	kg
Water		8.27E-05	m3

Table S10. LCI of electrolyte production for Li-Ion battery (Notter)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
ethylene carbonate	market for ethylene carbonate	0.894	kg
lithium hexafluorophosphate	market for lithium hexafluorophosphate	0.106	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Electrolyte for Li-Ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)	Electrolyte for Li-Ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)	1.00	kg

4.2. LFP battery

Two different inventory datasets are available for the LFP battery, based on the work by Majeau-Bettez et al. (Majeau-Bettez et al., 2011) and Zackrisson et al. (Zackrisson et al., 2010). The corresponding unified and parametrized inventory data are provided in Tables S11-S13 and S14-S17, respectively.

Table S11. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, LFP-C (Majeau-Bettez)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Cell_pack	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
Electrode substrate, anode, Li-Ion battery	acc. to Majeau-Bettez et al.	0.083/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrode substrate, cathode, Li-Ion battery	acc. to Majeau-Bettez et al.	0.036/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)	0.12/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Graphite anode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	0.08/0.6*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
LFP cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant	LFP cathode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	0.248/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Bauer)	Pack_housing	kg
precious metal refinery	market for precious metal refinery	1.9E-8/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	Item(s)
Separator, Li-Ion battery, at plant	acc. to Majeau-Bettez et al.	0.033/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.23	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.051	t*km
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	380.0/(0.6)*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Li-Ion battery pack, LFP-C, at plant (NTNU)	Li-Ion battery pack, LFP-C, at plant, modular (NTNU)	1	kg

Table S12. LCI of LFP cathode paste (Majeau-Bettez)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.08	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery carbon black	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters) market for carbon black carbon black	0	kg
LFP active material, at plant	acc. to Majeau-Bettez et al.	0.05	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	3.8	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.7	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
LFP cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	LFP cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	1.00	kg

Table S13. LCI of graphite anode paste, for LIB (Majeau-Bettez)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery graphite, battery grade	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters) market for graphite, battery grade	0.05	kg
heat, in chemical industry	market for heat, in chemical industry	0.95	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	5.00	MJ
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.2	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	0.1	t*km
Heat, waste		1.00	kg
		5.00	MJ

Table S14. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, LFP-C (Zackrisson)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	acc. to Ellingsen	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
LFP-C type Li-Ion Cell, at plant (Zackrisson, org)	LFP-C type Li-Ion Cell, modular, at plant (Zackrisson)	1-(Pack_housing+ BMS+ CoolSyst)	kg
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Bauer)	Pack_housing	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
LFP-C type Li-Ion Battery, at plant (Zackrisson, org.)	LFP-C type Li-Ion Battery, at plant, modular (Zackrisson, org.)	1.00	kg

Table S15. LCI of Li-Ion battery cell, LFP-C (Zackrisson)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Cell_pack	kg
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF ₆ , at plant	Electrolyte for Liion battery, 1M LiPF ₆ , at plant (Notter)	0.19535/(1-0.01267) * (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Graphite Anode, for Li-Ion battery	Graphite Anode, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Zackrisson)	0.24921/(1-0.012671) * (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
LFP-cathode, for Li-Ion battery	LFP-Cathode, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Zackrisson)	0.52376/(1-0.01267)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg

Separator, for Li-ion battery	Separator production, Li-ion battery (Zackrisson)	0.01901/((1-0.01267) * (1-Cell_Pack))	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
LFP-C type Li-Ion Cell, at plant	LFP-C type Li-Ion Cell, at plant, modular (Zackrisson, org)	1.00	kg

Table S16. LCI of LFP cathode paste (Zackrisson)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
aluminium, wrought alloy	market for aluminium, wrought alloy	0.03831	kg
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.05645	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black carbon black	0.05444	kg
LFP Cathode Material, at plant	LFP Cathode Material, at plant (Zackrisson, org)	0.85081	kg
sheet rolling, aluminium	market for sheet rolling, aluminium	0.03831	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
LFP-cathode, for Li-Ion battery (Zackrisson)	LFP-cathode, for Li-Ion battery (Zackrisson)	1.00	kg

Table S17. LCI of graphite anode paste (Zackrisson)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0.08898	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black carbon black	0	kg
copper	market for copper	0.19492	kg
graphite, battery grade	market for graphite, battery grade	0.7161	kg
sheet rolling, copper	market for sheet rolling, copper	0.19492	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Graphite Anode, for Li-Ion battery (Zackrisson)	Graphite Anode, for Li-Ion battery (Zackrisson)	1.00	kg

4.3. LTO battery

The parametrized inventory of the LFP-LTO battery is based on the work by Bauer (Bauer, 2010), who provides very aggregated inventory data. The corresponding LCI are given in Tables S18 and S19.

Table S18. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, LFP-LTO (Bauer)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
LFP-TiO Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery	LFP-TiO Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery, modular (Bauer)	1-(PackHousing+BMS+CoolSyst)	kg
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	PackHousing	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.0751	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.0251	t*km
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	0.0253	m3
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	25.3	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			

Table S19. LCI of Li-Ion battery cell, LFP-LTO (Bauer)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
aluminium, wrought alloy	market for aluminium, wrought alloy	0.128/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
benzene	market for benzene	0.0279/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.0167*0.6/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0.0167*0.4/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Cell_pack	kg
copper	market for copper	0.00296/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF6, at plant	Electrolyte for Liion battery, 1M LiPF6, at plant (Notter)	0.238/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
extrusion, plastic film	market for extrusion, plastic film	0.0759/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
iron sulfate	market for iron sulfate	0.209/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
lithium carbonate	market for lithium carbonate	0.0859/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
lithium hydroxide	market for lithium hydroxide	0.0981/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
nickel, 99.5%	market for nickel, 99.5%	0.00296/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
nitrogen, liquid	market for nitrogen, liquid	0.0387/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state	market for phosphoric acid, industrial grade, without water, in 85% solution state	0.134/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
polyethylene, linear low density, granulate	market for polyethylene, linear low density, granulate	0.038/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
polypropylene, granulate	polypropylene production, granulate	0.0378/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
sheet rolling, aluminium	market for sheet rolling, aluminium	0.128/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
sheet rolling, copper	market for sheet rolling, copper	0.00591/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
tap water	market for tap water	10.8/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
titanium dioxide	market for titanium dioxide	0.221/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.635	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.21	t*km
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	0.143/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	m3
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	135	kg
whey	market for whey	0.0196/(1-0.0171)*(1-Cell_Pack)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Carbon dioxide, fossil	to air	0.0486	kg
LFP-LTO Battery Cell, Li-Ion (Bauer)	LFP-LTO Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery	1.00	kg

4.3.1.NCM battery

As for the LFP battery, two different inventory datasets are available for the NCM battery, based on the work by Ellingsen et al. (Ellingsen et al., 2014) and Majeau-Bettez et al. (Majeau-Bettez et al., 2011). The corresponding unified and parametrized inventory data are provided in Tables S20-S25 and S26-S27, respectively. Since the graphite anode used by Majeau-Bettez is identical for the LFP and the NCM battery, the corresponding LCI (Table S13) is also valid for the NCM battery.

Table S20. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	CoolingSyst	kg

battery pack	(Ellingsen)		
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	PackHousing	kg
NCM-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery	NCM-C Battery Cell production, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	1-(PackHousing+BMS+CoolingSyst)	kg
precious metal refinery	market for precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.16	t*km
transport, freight, sea, transoceanic ship	market for transport, freight, sea, transoceanic ship	4.90	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C	Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C, modular (Ellingsen)	1.00	kg
Heat, waste		0.0014	MJ

Table S21. LCI of Li-Ion battery cell, NCM-C (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant (Ellingsen)	CellPack	kg
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, .LiPF6, at plant	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF6, at plant (Notter)	0.16/(1-6.64E-03) *	kg
Graphite anode, Li-Ion battery	Graphite anode production, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	0.39/(1-6.64E-03) *	kg
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	0	MJ
NCM Cathode, for Li-Ion battery	NCM Cathode production, for Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	0.43/(1-6.64E-03) *	kg
precious metal refinery	market for precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)
Separator, PP-based, for Li-Ion battery	acc. to Ellingsen et al.	0.022/(1-6.64E-03)*	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.26	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.1	t*km
water, decarbonised, at user	water production and supply, decarbonised	380	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCM-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	NCM-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	1.00	kg
Heat, waste		100	MJ

Table S22. LCI of a graphite anode, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Copper current collector, Li-Ion battery	acc. to Ellingsen et al.	0.57	kg
Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery	Graphite anode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (Ellingsen)	0.43	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.37	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.1	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
Graphite anode, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)		1.00	kg

Table S23. LCI of graphite anode paste, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC/PAA (Ellingsen)	0	kg

Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery chemical factory, organics	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0.04	kg
graphite, battery grade	chemical factory construction, organics	4.00E-10	Item(s)
transport, freight train	market for graphite, battery grade	0.96	kg
transport, freight, lorry	market for transport, freight train	1.2	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.19	t*km
Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	1.00	kg

Table S24. LCI of NCM cathode, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Aluminium current collector, for Li-Ion battery	acc. to Ellingsen et al.	0.11	kg
NCM cathode paste, for Li-Ion battery	NCM cathode paste production; modular (Ellingsen)	0.89	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.55	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.1	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCM Cathode, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	NCM Cathode, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	1.00	kg

Table S25. LCI of NCM cathode paste, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.04	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black carbon black	0.02	kg
chemical factory, organics	chemical factory construction, organics	4.00E-10	Item(s)
NCM active material, for Li-Ion battery	NCM active material production, for cathode, Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	0.94	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.46	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton,	0.14	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCM cathode paste, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	NCM cathode paste, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	1.00	kg

Table S26. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C (Majeau-Bettez)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Cell_pack	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
Electrode substrate, anode, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Electrode substrate, anode, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	0.083/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing- CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrode substrate, cathode, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Electrode substrate, cathode, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	0.036/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrolyte for Li-Ion battery, LiPF6, at plant	Electrolyte for Li-Ion battery, 1M LiPF6, at plant (Notter)	0.12/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing- CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg

Graphite anode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Graphite anode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	0.094/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	Pack_housing	kg
NCM cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant	NCM cathode paste production, Li-Ion battery, modular (NTNU)	0.232/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
precious metal refinery	market for precious metal refinery	1.90E-08	Item(s)
Separator, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Separator production, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	0.033/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.23	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.051	t*km
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	380.0/0.5980*(1-BMS-Pack_housing-CoolSyst-Cell_Pack)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C, at plant (NTNU)	Li-Ion battery pack, NCM-C, at plant (NTNU)	1.00	kg

Table S27. LCI of NCM cathode paste, for Li-Ion battery (Majeau-Bettez)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.08	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0	kg
carbon black	market for carbon black	0.05	kg
NCM active material, at plant	acc. to Majeau-Bettez et al.	0.87	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	3.8	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.7	t*km
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCM cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	NCM cathode paste, Li-Ion battery, at plant (NTNU)	1.00	kg

4.3.2.NCA battery

The LCI of the NCA battery is based on the work by Bauer (Bauer, 2010). Tables S28-S30 provide the corresponding inventory data.

Table S28. LCI of Li-Ion battery pack, NCA-C (Bauer)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
BMS, for Li-Ion battery, at plant	Battery management system (BMS) production, for LIB (Ellingsen)	BMS	kg
Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack	Cooling system, for Li-Ion battery pack (Ellingsen)	CoolSyst	kg
electricity, medium voltage	market group for electricity, medium voltage	kWhelManuf	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	MJthManuf	MJ
Li-Ion battery pack housing, at plant	Pack housing production, Li-Ion battery pack, at plant (Zackrisson / Bauer)	Pack_housing	kg
NCA-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery	NCA-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery, modular (Bauer)	1-(BMS+Pack_housing+CoolSyst)	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.0751	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.0249	t*km
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	0.0254	m3
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	25.3	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCA-C Battery Pack (Bauer)	NCA-C Battery Pack (Bauer)	1.00	kg

Table S29. LCI of Li-Ion battery cell, NCA-C (Bauer)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
aluminium, wrought alloy	market for aluminium, wrought alloy	0.0708/(1-0.015)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
benzene	market for benzene	0.0118/(1-0.015)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Binder, organic, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, organic (PVdF) (Bauer)	0.0099*0.6/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Binder, water based, for electrodes, Li-Ion battery	Binder production, for electrodes, Li-Ion batteries, CMC-SBR / water (Peters)	0.0099*0.4/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Cell container, Li-Ion battery, at plant	Cell container production, pouch incl. electrode tabs, for Li-Ion battery (Ellingsen)	Cell_pack	kg
copper	market for copper	0.1486/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, LiPF6, at plant extrusion, plastic film	Electrolyte for Li-ion battery, 1M LiPF6, at plant (Notter) market for extrusion, plastic film	0.18588/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack) 0.04165*2/(1-0.0146) * (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
Graphite, electrode quality	acc. to Bauer	0.196/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
NCA active material, Li-Ion battery	NCA active material, Li-Ion battery (Bauer)	0.27765/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
nickel, 99.5%	market for nickel, 99.5%	0.0025/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
polyethylene, low density, granulate	market for polyethylene, low density, granulate	0.0416/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
polypropylene, granulate	market for polypropylene, granulate	0.0416/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
sheet rolling, aluminium	market for sheet rolling, aluminium	0.0708/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
sheet rolling, copper	market for sheet rolling, copper	0.15106/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	0.301	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.101	t*km
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	0.141/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	m3
water, decarbonised, at user	market for water, decarbonised, at user	135.0/(1-0.0146)* (1-Cell_Pack)	kg
<i>Outputs</i>			
NCA-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery (Bauer)	NCA-C Battery Cell, Li-Ion battery (Bauer)	1.00	kg

Table S30. LCI of NCA active material (Bauer)

Flow	Provider	Amount	Unit
<i>Inputs</i>			
aluminium hydroxide	market for aluminium hydroxide	0.04	kg
cobalt	market for cobalt	0.09	kg
electricity, high voltage	market group for electricity, high voltage	1.88	kWh
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	2.96	MJ
hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	market for hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.46	kg
lithium hydroxide	market for lithium hydroxide	0.27	kg
nickel, 99.5%	market for nickel, 99.5%	0.49	kg
nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state	market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state	1.97	kg
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	1.25	kg
tap water	market for tap water	55	kg
transport, freight train	market for transport, freight train	1.37	t*km
transport, freight, lorry	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5	0.46	t*km
wastewater, average	market for wastewater, average	0.05	m3

<i>Outputs</i>			
NCA active material, Li-Ion battery (Bauer)	NCA active material, Li-Ion battery (Bauer)	1.00	kg
Nitrogen dioxide		1.37	kg

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